

Supporting Mental Health in Vancouver's South Asian Trucker Community - A Pilot Project

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Background and Context

The Trucking Profession

Across North America, trucking is recognized as a high-risk occupation. It is replete with a myriad of stressors and dangers; truck drivers are subject to

1. excessively long work hours with sedentary behaviour ¹⁻⁷;
2. irregular shift work disrupting sleep patterns ⁶⁻¹²;
3. psychological strain due to tightly run schedules and delivery pressures ^{3, 6-7, 13-15};
4. chronic social isolation ^{1, 3-5, 16-17};
5. work-life conflict ^{1,18};
6. driving in challenging weather conditions ¹⁹⁻²¹;
7. exposure to hazardous levels of diesel exhaust fumes ²²⁻²³ and excessive noise ²⁴⁻²⁶.

The multitude of stressors that truck drivers face in their profession exposes them to a disproportionate level of risk, as compared to other occupations, to their health, safety, and wellbeing. The extant literature unanimously identifies detrimental ramifications of such a work context on the physical and psychological wellbeing of truck drivers.

Studies have identified higher rates of cardiometabolic diseases ^{1, 6, 13-14, 18, 27} such as hypertension, diabetes and hypercholesterolemia, and musculoskeletal disorders and problems like lower-back and sciatic pain in truck drivers ^{1, 13-14, 28} as compared to the general population. The trucking industry has perpetuated a work culture wherein truck drivers are overworked and fatigued, and face disturbances to obtaining sufficient sleep, exercise, and a healthy diet. The lifestyle variables associated with the job scope make these truck drivers more vulnerable to diseases, disorders, and overall poor physical health.

Moreover, the psychological burden of the job puts a strain on their mental health, as evinced by the high rates of psychiatric disorders and symptoms reported by truck drivers^{2, 3, 7, 9, 13, 17, 29-31} such as anxiety, depression, risk-taking behaviour, substance use and sleep disorders. Research has highlighted the strong association between psychosocial factors, depressive symptoms, and substance use³²⁻³⁵. Unfortunately, protective factors such as family-bonding and support are lacking in many drivers' lives, given their long hours away from home^{7, 10, 16, 36-37}. Moreover, the hyper-masculine work environment in the trucking industry is laden with stigma against seeking support for mental health, causing drivers to downplay and dismiss any mental health problems they may be facing, which in turn tends to exacerbate them further^{4, 7, 38-40}.

Use of substances^{7, 31, 41-42}, typically psychostimulants such as amphetamines, is also common amongst truckers. These are considered a useful strategy⁴² for fatigue management and increased focus on roads amidst the long continuous hours of driving. Unrestrained use of substances can spiral to serious substance use disorders which have detrimental impacts on both physical and mental health. Moreover, use of stimulants (or problematic substance use) has been associated with increased risky driving behaviour and poorer compliance with traffic regulations⁴³, as well as overall increased risk of crashes⁴⁴⁻⁴⁵. This carries grave repercussions not just for truck drivers, but also the general population.

The Trucker Community in the Lower Mainland

Demographics

As of 2022, there are approximately 38,370 people working in the transportation trucking industry in British Columbia (BC), and 22,940 in the Lower Mainland ⁴⁶. The industry is male-dominated; over 95% of truckers were male compared to 52% for all occupations, though this is a slight development from the 97% recorded in 2016 ⁴⁸. According to the 2016 Census, 53% of truckers in BC were reported to be between the ages of 45 and 64 ⁴⁷. Reports in 2021 show 93% of truckers as full-time employees, with 69% having a high school diploma or less as their highest level of education ⁴⁸.

The 2022 BC Labour Market Outlook projected 12,340 job openings for truckers between 2022 and 2032 in BC, 6450 of which are in the Lower Mainland ⁴⁶.

According to the Ontario Trucking Association (2016) ⁴⁹, 17.8% and 34.6% of truck drivers in Canada and BC respectively, were of South Asian background. In Vancouver alone, 55.9% of truck drivers were immigrants from South Asia ⁴⁹. It is important to note that the ‘South Asian background’ is an umbrella term representing any person who identifies with an ethnicity associated with the southern part of Asia, which constitutes a myriad of ethnic, religious and linguistic communities, some of which are characterized as Bangladeshi, Bengali, East Indian, Goan, Gujarati, Hindu, Ismaili, Kashmiri, Nepali, Pakistani, Punjabi, Sikh, Sinhalese, or Sri Lankan ⁵⁰.

The South Asian Majority

The majority of the truckers in Canada who identify as South Asian are immigrants ⁵¹. The 2022 BC Labour Market Outlook reported 4,570 immigrants in BC ⁴⁶. There has been a shift in the demographic of workers in the Lower Mainland over the past 30 years, whereby the proportion of South Asian immigrants has remarkably increased, with many turning toward the transportation industry. In 1991, 25.2% and 38% of drivers in Canada and Vancouver respectively were cited as immigrants from India, and in 2016, the percentages had risen up to 69.9% and 70.5% respectively ⁵¹. As of 2018, around 95% of truckers in Delta, an area in the Lower Mainland, were reported to be of South Asian background ⁵¹.

There is a paucity of data presenting the breakdown of the South Asian backgrounds of truckers in Canada. At best, reports by Newcom Media show that 43.7% of truckers in Canada identified themselves as Indian ⁵¹.

“Whether you were born and raised in Canada or you were a new immigrant, the trucking industry didn’t seem to discriminate, but rather provided opportunity to those who were willing to work hard. It gave many of the South Asians an opportunity to earn a good living, and to be able to provide for their families.”

- Daman Grewal, the co-owner of Centurion Trucking, a for-hire carrier out of Surrey, B.C., that specializes in hauling temperature-controlled shipments throughout Canada and the U.S ⁵¹.

Systemic Issues in the Trucking Industry

The slew of stressors that comes with a profession in truck driving have been discussed, but there is also a need for recognition of the issues that exist at a systemic level. These issues instigate the rapidly increasing stressors that truckers in the Lower Mainland have to face, contributing to poorer mental health and wellbeing.

Shortage of Parking Spaces

In recent years, truck drivers in BC have been advocating and raising complaints on the critical lack of parking spaces for truck drivers to park in a safe, legal and cost-effective manner. Trucks utilized in long-haul trucking typically weigh 5,000 kilograms⁵², which requires a large lot to park safely. As the market size for the trucking industry has expanded over the years, so have the number of trucks in the Lower Mainland in order to meet the growing demands⁵³⁻⁵⁴. The number of parking spots for trucks however have not been proportionately accounted for, leaving many truck drivers no choice but to park illegally, such as on the side of residential streets, or private properties⁵⁴⁻⁵⁵. Some drivers have turned to private landowners to rent spaces on their properties, but the fees for doing so have doubled over the past five years, going upwards of \$700 per month. Hence, not only do truckers have to compromise their safety and that of others by parking illegally, they also incur costs for parking tickets, which in sum can cost a company between \$1,000 to \$1,500 monthly.

Inadequate Driver Training

According to the 2018 BC Auditor's Report, heavy commercial vehicles are involved in 19% of fatal accidents in BC, despite representing only 3% of vehicles on the roads⁵⁶. The report also found that while some BC agencies, such as ICBC, PSSG and TRAN, have been involved in commercial vehicle safety-related education and promotion, there has been insufficient effort to evaluate the effectiveness of their programs. Additionally, the report did not identify any comprehensive efforts or resources committed to ensuring commercial vehicle safety for truckers in BC.

Up till October 2021, there did not exist any minimum entry-level training standards for long-haul truckers in BC⁵⁷. Despite the convoluted challenges that come with driving a motor vehicle that weighs more than 5,000 kilograms

and goes up to 72 feet long, for extended hours, and in challenging weather conditions, truckers only required a Class 1 license, easily obtained following a 16-hour air brake course and two knowledge tests before their road test. Moreover, despite the regular occurrence of drivers crossing provincial borders en route, there are no federal regulations on driver training, as it is under provincial and territorial jurisdiction⁵⁸. This can pose a challenge to truckers who lack the training needed to drive in other provinces in a confident and safe manner.

The 2018 Humboldt Bus Crash

One of Canada's worst road tragedies, the Humboldt Broncos crash claimed 16 lives and 13 injuries in the Humboldt Broncos Junior Hockey Team near Armley, Saskatchewan⁵⁹⁻⁶². The cause of the accident was traced back to 29-year-old truck driver Jaskirat Singh Sidhu, who was then driving a semi-truck carrying a double load, on one of his first solo jobs as a trucker. Jaskirat obtained his commercial license after undergoing only one week of training and two weeks of supervised driving, with no previous experience in the industry. He had failed to yield at a stop sign at the intersection of Highways 35 and 335, which resulted in a collision with the bus carrying the Humboldt Broncos.

This fatal accident revealed the extensive gaps in Canada's trucking safety and training standards, spurring a national call for ministers to improve and enforce mandatory training for truck drivers⁶³⁻⁶⁶. This resulted in the development of the National Safety Code (NSC) in 2020 by the Canadian Council of Motor Transport Administrators, which included training for Class 1 commercial truck drivers known as MELT (Mandatory Entry Level Training)⁶⁷⁻⁶⁸.

On October 18 2021, BC became the fifth province to officially implement MELT^{57, 68-69}. The new training encompasses 140 hours in total that includes additional behind-the-wheel driving hours, in-yard hours and theoretical instructional hours, as well as climate-specific driver training^{57, 70-71}. However, the MELT requirement does not apply to truckers who had obtained their Class 1 license prior to 2021, meaning a large cohort of truckers continue to drive on the roads without formal, standardized training^{57, 71}. No concerted efforts have been made provincially to provide these truckers with education and training programs to meet the NSC standards that would allow them to operate confidently and safely on the roads. As such, this remains a significant stressor for truckers in the Lower Mainland.

Labour Shortages

The North American trucking industry is currently facing rampant labour shortages. The Canadian Trucking Alliance reports a projected shortage of 55,000 workers at the end of 2023⁷². Trucking HR Canada however, expects an annual hire of 17,230 new truck drivers up until 2025 to meet the rapidly increasing demand⁷³. Turnover rates have climbed up to as high as 90 percent, contributing to the estimated gap of more than 25,000 drivers in the Canadian industry⁷⁴. As a result, companies have faced unprecedented financial burdens from the delayed shipment of goods⁷⁴, and unseated trucks that require support, maintenance or payments⁷⁵.

In 2021 itself, labour shortage was ranked as the top issue of concern amongst 87% of trucking senior executives consulted in a research study conducted by the Canadian Trucking Alliance⁷⁵. Yet, since then, the issue has only exacerbated, as was foreseen by the participants in the study that had called attention to the need for increased governmental efforts to address the contributing factors of the labour shortage.

On top of the myriad of issues that had materialized from the COVID-19 pandemic, another causative element of the labour shortage is the hike in training costs. Since the implementation of the MELT training requirement that can cost up to \$16,000, the cost of training new truck drivers has risen dramatically⁷⁶. Certain grant opportunities are provided by the BC government to help offset these costs, but the funding support is not nearly enough to attract more truckers into the industry. For example, the WorkBC Centre Services instates a \$7,500 tuition maximum, which means that individuals still have to seek additional financial channels to fulfill more than half of the training costs⁷⁷. An alternative funding opportunity is the BC Employer Training Grant, which provides employers 80% of the cost of training up to \$10,000 per participant annually⁷⁷. Once again, this still leaves employers to fund a significant portion of the Class 1 MELT training, or shift the burden to the trainees themselves.

Problems Emergent from the COVID-19 Pandemic

Compounding the already high burden of poor mental health amongst truck drivers, the COVID-19 pandemic introduced a flood of issues into the trucker community. According to a study by Sperry et al. that collected data from workers in the trucking industry, more than half the participants reported that COVID-19 affected their work by increasing work stress, health risks, and work

ours ⁷⁸. Numerous truck drivers experienced heightened stress and adverse physical, psychological and social health outcomes stemming from the various challenges arising from the COVID-19 pandemic ⁷⁸⁻⁸¹.

Increased Work Burden

In common with many markets, the pandemic had a major impact on the demand for the trucking industry. The COVID-19 lockdowns across Canada propelled a shift in the demand for deliveries ^{78, 82-84}. Statistics Canada reported a 99.3 percent increase in e-commerce sales from February to May 2020, as consumers turned to online shopping and businesses boosted their online platforms following sudden in-person store closures. Even as restrictions were lifted, e-commerce sales continued to stabilize at levels above those observed pre-pandemic, at a 67.9% jump from 2020 to 2022. The change in consumer behaviour had motivated businesses to invest in their online sale capacities, which in turn maintained the surge in demand for the delivery of goods.

70% of all freight tonnage including essential items such as medical supplies and food, as well as retail commodities and goods are delivered by trucks ⁸⁴. The increased demand for the delivery of these goods translated into an increased demand for the trucking industry. However, this demand was not met with a proportionate rise in resources for the trucking industry. Primarily, labour shortage remained a pertinent issue, wherein the dearth of truckers made it difficult for them to meet the increase in demand, exacerbating the already existing labour shortages. With few drivers available, those on the road faced longer hours and increased pressure to complete more deliveries ^{78-80, 85}. The rise to e-commerce further intensified these pressures, as consumer expectations for overnight delivery and low prices pushed companies to expedite delivery schedules, leading to rushed and stressful work conditions ⁸⁶⁻⁸⁸.

Moreover, while the pandemic had resulted in an upward shift of consumer demand, it had the opposing effect on the global supply chain. Critical points at manufacturing, shipping, port operations, and warehousing faced delays and closures given labour shortages and mandatory shutdowns during the pandemic ⁷⁸. This shifted the burden of keeping up with delivery demands on to truck drivers, further intensifying workloads, work hours and overall stress. ^{79, 89-91}.

Access to Driver Amenities

The availability of amenities including rest areas, food services, sanitary facilities, and secure parking, is fundamental to the health, safety, and overall well-being of truck drivers. These amenities provide opportunities for drivers to take much-needed rest breaks, maintain proper nutrition and personal hygiene, as well as find safe locations to park and recuperate during long and irregular work hours ⁷⁹⁻⁸⁰. Without reliable access to such facilities, drivers face exacerbated physical fatigue and psychological distress ^{1, 14}. Unfortunately, the COVID-19 pandemic widely disrupted drivers' access to these amenities. In an effort to curb the spread of the virus, many public and private facilities - including rest stops, restaurants, bars, diners, convenience stores, gas stations and shower facilities - were either temporarily closed or operated under strict health and safety protocols ^{78, 81, 92-96}. These restrictions denied truck drivers access to food, hygiene services, restrooms, and safe places to rest or sleep during long-haul journeys, which increased physical and psychological stress ^{78-81, 92-96}. The denial of access to restrooms and basic facilities has had profoundly dehumanizing effects on truck drivers, as they are left with unsanitary alternatives, such as “the bush”, or even the last resort to “just hold it and carry on” ⁹⁴. Some drivers have even taken Ubers to find washrooms they could use ⁹⁵.

“One female truck driver, she said, told her how she'd been unloading at a facility for six hours without being allowed to use the facilities — and when she asked a third time, was given a roll of toilet paper and told to go behind the building. Drivers are human beings. We're not dogs. We don't go outside.”

- Shelley Uvanile-Hesch, CEO of the Women's Trucking Federation of Canada ⁹⁶.

Vulnerability to COVID-19

Truck drivers faced heightened vulnerability to COVID-19 due to the inherent nature of their work making them essential workers during the pandemic^{78-81, 97-99}. In the US for example, it was reported that the transportation/logistics sector had one of the highest per-capita excess mortality rates due to COVID-19¹⁰⁰⁻¹⁰¹. As essential frontline workers, truck drivers had frequent and unavoidable contact with individuals at various loading docks and delivery points, including in areas known to be COVID hotspots^{78-81, 97-99}. Yet, they were marginalized in pandemic response efforts - they had limited access to basic personal protective equipment (PPE), as well as delayed inclusion in vaccination programs^{78-81, 97-99}. Their vulnerability to COVID-19 was further intensified by the closure of rest stops and service centers, which significantly restricted opportunities to practice basic hygiene, such as handwashing and sanitization^{78-81, 92-96}. Moreover, a large proportion of truckers, particularly older and racialized workers, faced compounded health risks, as this demographic was already more susceptible to severe COVID-19 outcome⁹⁹. Understandably, these systemic gaps and lack of protection served as persistent stressors that jeopardized not only their physical health, but also their psychological well-being⁷⁸⁻⁹⁹.

In addition to the heightened risks of COVID-19 exposure, truck drivers struggled significantly with the separation from their families and communities, prolonged by lockdowns and travel restrictions. This was especially seen in South Asian truckers, given their strong identification with collectivist family values and extended kin relations¹⁰²⁻¹⁰³. For example, Punjabi truckers in the Lower Mainland were documented to express fear, loneliness and frustration over the loss of in-person community interaction, such as visits to gurdwaras and family gatherings, on top of the increased occupational risks they faced and the delayed access to vaccination resources despite being essential workers¹⁰⁴.

Public Perception of Truckers

The public perception of truckers had unfortunately deteriorated over the pandemic, acting as an additional stressor for truck drivers during this challenging period. Historically, truck drivers have had a largely negative image in the public, stereotyping them as reckless, poorly educated, unprofessional and unhygienic¹⁰⁵⁻¹⁰⁶. Harmful stereotypes were further perpetuated over the pandemic, as truck drivers were portrayed as high-risk carriers of COVID-19 due to their occupational exposure, and perceived lack of hygienic practices -

though these conditions directly resulted from COVID-influenced amenity closures and blocked access to sanitation facilities ^{79-81, 105}. In Canada, these negative portrayals were aggravated by racial biases, disproportionately targeting South Asian truckers. For example, Premier Jason Kenney in Alberta publicly attributed the spread of COVID-19 to the South Asian community, claiming they had “big family gatherings at home” as a part of their cultural practices ¹⁰⁷. These claims had been disproved later due to the lack of empirical evidence that the South Asian community had held large gatherings over the pandemic; nevertheless, the false narrative had already spread widely, reinforcing stigmatization and racial bias against the community.

2022 Freedom Convoy

The 2022 Freedom Convoy ¹⁰⁸ protests played a significant role in damaging the public perception of truck drivers. The protests had started in January 2022, as a peaceful act in response to COVID-19 vaccine mandates and pandemic-related restrictions for cross-border truck drivers. However, it quickly escalated into a dangerous and disruptive movement associated with anti-government sentiments and civil disobedience - the protests were declared a national emergency and deemed an illegal occupation of Ottawa. Unfortunately, the protests that were initiated with the intention of advocating for truckers’ freedom to work, had drawn in right-wing crowds, some of whom displayed Confederate flags and other extremist symbols, shifting the tone of the movement. Participants engaged in acts of vandalism and destruction of property, harassment of citizens, and blockage of major roads. Illegal blockades were near ports of entry across cities, which significantly disrupted the flow of goods and services, while also creating hazardous traffic conditions and public safety concerns. Law enforcement agencies were eventually compelled to intervene; for instance, a blockade in Coutts, Alberta, which had disrupted trade for over two weeks, resulted in the arrest of 13 individuals and the seizure of firearms and ammunition. Additionally, four men were charged with conspiracy to murder Royal Canadian Mounted Police officers.

The public unrest created by the convoy reinforced negative stereotypes about truckers and further contributed to their stigmatization, as they became increasingly associated with violence and dissent. Media coverage of the protests additionally emphasized the disruptions caused by the convoy, framing truck drivers as hostile and antagonistic individuals ¹⁰⁹⁻¹¹². As the Freedom Convoy became associated with disruption, aggression and radical political views, the public extended these stereotypes to all truckers.

Notably however, nearly 90% of Canadian truck drivers were reported to be fully vaccinated, indicating that the movement did not represent the sentiments of the general trucker community. Indeed, South Asian truckers across Canada - who make up the majority of the trucker community - expressed strong opposition to the Freedom Convoy, emphasizing the lack of representation of South Asians in the movement, which predominantly constituted White Canadians ¹¹³⁻¹¹⁵. They instead voiced their support for the administration of vaccinations, emphasizing their dedication to public health and the safety of their families - particularly given that many immigrants reside in multigenerational households with elderly relatives who are more vulnerable to COVID-19 ¹¹³⁻¹¹⁴. Supporting this, Statistics Canada reports 82.5% of the South Asian population expressed willingness to receive the COVID vaccine ¹¹⁶.

“This convoy is kind of purporting to represent all truckers, but a lot of South Asian truckers have literally just been working away during the pandemic, trying to keep their family safe.”

- Kulpreet Singh, founder of the South Asian Mental Health Alliance ¹¹⁷.

Not only did the trucker community showcase strong disagreements with the Freedom Convoy’s anti-vaccine agenda, they also expressed concern and frustration that the protests distracted from more pressing issues affecting the trucking industry ¹¹³⁻¹¹⁴. Representatives from the trucking community emphasized the need to advocate for systemic issues affecting the industry - including unsafe working conditions, labour shortages, lack of rest stops and parking areas - which the Freedom Convoy was taking attention away from ^{113-114,}

¹¹⁸⁻¹²⁰

Despite the clear opposition of the majority of truck drivers to the Freedom Convoy, media portrayals of the protests failed to distinguish between participants and the broader trucker community, implicating many South Asian truckers in the negative fallout of the movement ¹¹⁵. The Freedom Convoy not only damaged the reputation of South Asian drivers and further stigmatized them, but also overshadowed their distinct experiences and advocacy efforts to highlight the systemic issues in the trucking industry.

South Asian Men and Mental Health

South Asian men encounter unique mental health challenges shaped by cultural values, gender norms, stigma, and systemic barriers. Despite the prevalence of mental distress in South Asian populations, they remain underrepresented in mental health research and underserved by mental health care systems ¹²¹. Stigma poses a significant barrier to mental health care in South Asian communities. For South Asian men in particular, the stigma is aggravated by cultural values and perceptions of masculinity - norms that emphasize emotional stoicism, resilience, and self-reliance ¹²²⁻¹²³. These ideals reinforce the notion that experiencing mental health challenges is a sign of weakness or a threat to one's masculinity, often shaming men into silence and deterring them from seeking help, even if experiencing significant distress ¹²²⁻¹²⁷.

Moreover, the culturally defined role of men in many South Asian families is closely tied to duty, sacrifice and provision, wherein South Asian men are viewed as the backbone of the household, responsible for ensuring the family's social and financial stability. These expectations are further reinforced by collectivist cultural values that prioritize conformity, family cohesion, and group welfare over individual needs. As a result, many South Asian men choose to internalize their psychological struggles rather than risk straying from their role as anchors within their families. Seeking support or even acknowledging emotional distress can be associated with bringing dishonour to their families, exacerbating the stigma against mental health. Indeed, several studies have identified culturally rooted stigma within South Asian immigrant families as a key factor impeding help-seeking behaviours ¹²¹⁻¹²⁷.

Mainstream mental health services largely adopt Western models of mental health care, which often fail to adequately address the unique cultural values and lived experiences of South Asian men. These models typically emphasize traits such as individualism and open emotional disclosure, which contrast sharply with South Asian values that prioritize collectivism and emotional restraint instead. Moreover, mental health providers may often lack cultural sensitivity and competence, holding certain assumptions of normative family dynamics or gender roles that differ from those of their patients. As a result, many South Asian men experience a sense of disconnect between their cultural conceptualizations of mental health and the frameworks prevalent in Western mental health services. The lack of cultural responsiveness among mental health providers has indeed been documented as a key barrier that hinder the utilization of mental health services among South Asian communities and contribute to their early disengagement from mental health care ¹²¹⁻¹²⁸.

Health Interventions for Truck Drivers

Despite the plethora of negative health outcomes associated with long-haul truck driving, there has been little to no research or implementation of health promotion and protection interventions for truck drivers. The few interventions that have been executed however, have resulted in improved intermediate health outcomes (i.e., body mass index [BMI], body fat percentage) and health behaviours for truck drivers (i.e., nutrition, physical activity) ¹²⁹⁻¹³². These interventions incorporated various components of health habits – smoking cessation, weight loss, fatigue management, nutrition and exercise promotion, as well as health education efforts. It is pertinent to note that these interventions have focused on the improvement of physical health only, and efforts have yet to be made for improving the mental health and wellbeing of truck drivers. This emphasises the importance of developing an intervention targeting mental health promotion and education for truck drivers, especially given that the literature illustrates high incidence of poor mental health outcomes in truck drivers.

In the Lower Mainland of BC, this need is particularly salient due to the numerous systemic issues in the trucking industry that have been previously discussed, as well as the predominantly racialized composition of the trucker community which further compounds their barriers and stressors.

Pilot Mental Health Intervention

Overview

In response to these intersecting challenges, SAMHAA has mobilized community-based efforts to support the wellbeing of South Asian truck drivers, with generous donations from the community to our fundraiser on GoFundMe¹³³. We initiated a pilot project implementing culturally responsive mental health workshops for South Asian truck drivers in the Lower Mainland, with the aim of promoting awareness and mental health literacy, as well as reducing stigma, through inclusive, language-sensitive outreach and peer engagement.

SAMHAA delivered two community-based, culturally responsive mental health workshops for 15 Punjabi-speaking South Asian truck drivers in the Lower Mainland. The workshops were held on May 28, 2023 and August 13, 2023 at Surrey. They were facilitated in Punjabi by bilingual (English & Punjabi) South Asian facilitators with experience in community mental health outreach, including a registered psychologist from Moving Forward Family Services. Both sessions were conducted in a conversational, discussion-based format and incorporated Punjabi-language terminology and culturally-relevant examples to enhance accessibility and engagement. The design of the workshops were intended to normalize conversations about mental health and wellbeing, while promoting mental health literacy and equipping participants with practical strategies for emotional regulation and self-care within the context of the trucking industry.

Each workshop followed a participatory structure that combined:

- Guided group discussion;
- Education using culturally adapted terminology;
- Mental wellbeing exercises; and
- Peer sharing and reflection

We shifted away from an instructional approach and instead emphasized the creation of a safe, stigma-free space for discussion, which allowed participants to express mental health concepts and lived experiences in their own words and within their own cultural frameworks.

Workshop Delivery

Workshop Session 1

The first workshop, held on May 28, 2023, aimed to introduce basic concepts related to mental health and wellbeing, laying the groundwork for open dialogue between participants.

Discussion Questions

Participants were invited to discuss the following questions:

- What do you do to deal with these emotions like sadness, anger, or worry?
- Have you heard about the term mental health?
- Do you think it is necessary to take care of your *mansik sihat* (mental wellbeing)?
- What do you do to maintain good mental wellbeing in your personal life?
- Do you think it is still a taboo to talk about mental health in the South Asian Community? Is talking openly about mental health something that is frowned upon or shameful or are people shy about this?
- In this industry, what are the challenges and barriers for those who want to talk about their mental health or feelings?
- What do you do to improve your self-esteem? How do you keep yourself confident? Do you have thoughts, belief, perspective on this? How do you maintain it?

Content and Themes

Staying in the Present and Emotional Regulation	We began the workshop by practicing simple breathing and grounding exercises collectively, which acted as the foundation for facilitators to explain physiological responses associated with stress and anxiety (e.g., increased heart rate, sweating, muscle tension). Participants were encouraged to reflect on how past worries and anxieties had triggered similar responses.
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<p>Culturally Adapted Mental Health Terminology</p>	<p>Facilitators explained that in South Asian communities, the term ‘mental’ is often associated with being dimagi (crazy), and contrasted this with a normalized understanding of mental health as dimag di sehat (health of the mind). This approach aimed to tackle a key source of stigma perpetuation in South Asian communities. By placing emphasis on ‘health’ and drawing parallels to physical health, facilitators reinforced that mental wellbeing is an essential part of human functioning.</p>
<p>Importance of Mental Health in Daily Functioning</p>	<p>Facilitators further highlighted how mental health directly affects one’s ability to maintain their daily functioning. Mental wellbeing was portrayed as essential to participants’ employment, safety and quality of life.</p>
<p>Factors Influencing Mental Health</p>	<p>Facilitators distinguished between mental illness, and mental health challenges that arise from external stressors such as inflation, workplace demands, or financial pressures. This enabled participants to relate to their own experiences and reduce stigma by framing mental health challenges as universal and justified responses to life circumstances, rather than illnesses - which is often the source of fear around being labeled or judged. Participants were encouraged to reflect on what they personally do to maintain a healthy mindset and emotional balance when encountering stressors.</p>
<p>Stigma, Taboo, and Industry-Specific Challenges</p>	<p>Facilitators acknowledged the stigma surrounding mental health in South Asian communities, including shame, reluctance to speak openly, and fears of judgement. They also explored trucking-specific barriers to mental wellbeing, such as isolation and long work hours.</p>
<p>Emotional Wellbeing and Self-Esteem</p>	<p>Facilitators introduced emotional wellbeing as a skill that can be developed over time. Key concepts included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness of one’s own emotions and the emotions of others; • Emotional regulation through grounding strategies; • Differentiating healthy self-esteem from egotism; • Recognizing and challenging self-deprecating thoughts; and • Practicing confidence, self-respect, and boundary-setting (e.g., learning to say no without guilt). <p>Participants were encouraged to view emotional regulation as a skill for them to learn and hone, rather than an innate trait, emphasizing practice and consistency.</p>

Substance Use and Coping	Facilitators addressed substance use as a coping mechanism that is often present but rarely discussed within the community. They acknowledged that alcohol and drug consumption are common responses to stress in many individuals. To facilitate an informed and open discussion, a Punjabi video from Fraser Health Authority, Talk to your child , was screened. This was a public health message as part of an awareness campaign to reduce substance-use harm in South Asian communities and help prevent overdose deaths.
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Workshop Session 2

The second workshop, held on August 13, 2023, built upon concepts introduced in the first session and expanded into strengthening psychological wellbeing, social connectedness, and community support, and more in-depth discussion of substance use, addiction, and harm reduction. As with the first workshop, the session was facilitated in a bilingual, culturally responsive format and emphasized participant reflection and dialogue.

Discussion Questions

Participants were invited to discuss the following questions:

- What can be done to strengthen our psychological wellbeing?
- When you think about social wellbeing, what comes to mind? What could make your social wellbeing stronger?
- How can we keep our social connections and community stronger?
- What are your thoughts on this video? (*see Content and Themes for information on video screened*)
- What is the difference between regular use and addiction?

Content and Themes

Staying in the Present and Emotional Regulation	The workshop opened with guided breathing exercises, reinforcing techniques introduced in the first session. Religious and spiritual practices familiar to participants were integrated into the exercise, with facilitators suggesting the use of prayer or repetition of spiritually meaningful words during breathing, integrating cultural resonance into the session.
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Psychological Wellbeing	Facilitators introduced psychological wellbeing as the ability to recognize, understand, and respond to changes in one’s mental state. They highlighted the importance of trusting one’s own abilities, and were encouraged to reflect on how their past experiences and stressors had disrupted their psychological balance.
Strengthening Psychological Wellbeing	A key component of the workshop was focused on identifying and challenging negative thought patterns. Facilitators explained how negative thought patterns can contribute to negative emotions and behaviours (e.g., anxiety, avoidance, distress). The interconnectedness between emotions, behaviour and physiological senses was highlighted to portray how each domain could be utilized to strengthen psychological wellbeing overall. Cognitive strategies to reframe and challenge negative thought patterns were practiced, alongside grounding and breathing exercises. Lifestyle factors including sleep, physical activity, and nutrition were also discussed as integral aspects of psychological wellbeing.
Social Wellbeing: Relationships	Facilitators introduced social wellbeing as cultivating meaningful, supportive connections. As truck drivers who face long working hours and isolation, social wellbeing was acknowledged as challenging to maintain. Participants were encouraged to make the effort to foster supportive relationships with families and friends. Strategies to do so were discussed, including open communication, shared activities, and prioritizing regular in-person interactions over digital communication.
Social Wellbeing: Positive Influences and Community	Facilitators illustrated how positive social environments, such as spending time with supportive friends and family, engaging in community events, or participating in seva (selfless service) contribute to one’s social wellbeing. They also emphasized the importance of community, namely how one’s social circle can directly influence one’s personal habits, values, and emotional health, which in turn impacts one’s wellbeing.
Substance Use Education	Facilitators reviewed commonly used substances and basic substance categories. They discussed how substances may initially seem to reduce stress but can impair judgment, coordination, and mental health over time. They delved into addiction, framing it as a health condition involving physical and psychological dependence, rather than a personal weakness or moral failing. Facilitators highlighted the importance of compassion, treatment and recovery in one’s addiction journey, while challenging associated stigma and shame in society.

Substance Use Education: Treatment, Resources, and Harm Reduction	Facilitators discussed available treatment options, including counselling, support groups, family physicians, and rehabilitation services, with an emphasis on culturally and linguistically accessible resources. They discussed the opioid epidemic in the Lower Mainland, including toxic drug supply and high overdose rates. Harm reduction was then introduced as a pragmatic approach that prioritizes safety, dignity, and survival.
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Cultural Adaptation

Cultural adaptation was a key consideration in the delivery of the workshops, given the stigma surrounding mental health in South Asian communities, and the limited efficacy of Western psychoeducation interventions when applied without curation to cultural and contextual needs. Facilitators established a culturally resonant framework for discussing mental health by integrating cultural concepts and meaningful terminology, such as *seva* (selfless service) or *dimag di sehat* (health of the mind), allowing for nuanced and relatable discussions during the workshops. Religion and spirituality were also incorporated into the workshops; for example, the use of prayer during breathing exercises. Connecting traditional values with modern mental health concepts was also crucial to ensuring that discussions were impactful and memorable to them, fostering meaningful engagement during the workshops. For example, discussions were framed around family and collective wellbeing, as opposed to Western models of individualistic wellbeing. Cultural adaptation of the workshop delivery allowed participants to engage with mental health concepts in ways that aligned with their values and lived experiences, thereby reducing stigma and encouraging sustainable takeaways.

Discussion Findings

Conceptualizations of Mental Health

Participants shared diverse and nuanced conceptualizations of mental health that encompassed physiological, behavioural, cultural, social, and spiritual dimensions.

Mental health was described as closely linked to physical processes in the body, including changes in blood pressure and the balance of hormones such as serotonin and cortisol. Participants viewed mental health as the brain's response to both positive and negative life experiences. For example, one participant explained that engaging in meaningful activities like volunteering can trigger the release of “feel-good” hormones, highlighting how such actions can positively influence mental wellbeing. Medication was also perceived as a tool that can help restore our biological balance of chemicals and hormones when disrupted.

Behavioural manifestations of mental health were framed in terms of emotional instability and aggression. Participants described situations where conflicts had escalated rapidly in their lives, at times even resulting in severe violence, and highlighted these as a perceived lack of emotional regulation and control within their communities.

The terminology of mental health in Punjabi itself was discussed in relation to their understanding of mental health. There was recognition that use of the term “mental” in Punjabi was commonly associated with “crazy”, or “mentally sick”, and often held a derogatory or negative connotation to it. Participants acknowledged that this language contributes to stigma around mental health and wellbeing, amplifying shame and judgement that create additional barriers to open discussion. Cultural norms were further noted to reinforce stigma surrounding mental health; values emphasizing privacy, judgement and social reputation within the Punjabi community were noted to perpetuate silence and stigma in response to stressors that negatively impact mental wellbeing. On the other hand, participants noted that religious teachings in Sikhism positively shape their understanding of mental wellbeing, where core values of acceptance and spiritual trust played a central role. For example, one participant explained that according to Gurbani, “even a leaf does not move without divine will”, illustrating that life circumstances are ultimately beyond one's control. This perspective was noted to help frame mental wellbeing through a lens of

acceptance and faith that allows one to develop resilience when encountering adversity.

Otherwise, mental health was widely acknowledged among participants as essential to overall functioning, including family wellbeing, work capacity, social relationships, and physical health. Participants expressed that mental health was critical to maintain in the context of fulfilling responsibilities to their families and community. In relation to their commitment to and sense of duty, mental health was also framed as one's strength of mind. The ability to cope with stress, uphold social connections, and perform daily responsibilities was seen as a sign of a strong mind. Participants described how failure to do so, or reliance on substances or medications to perform, might indicate a "weak mind", not yet strong or resilient.

Participants frequently used vivid analogues and metaphors to articulate their understanding and experience of mental wellbeing. One analogy compared mental stress to water filling a bottle throughout the day, where each negative experience accumulates until it overflows, demonstrating how daily stressors build and become difficult to manage. Mental wellbeing was also likened to climbing stairs, where progress is gradual and requires persistent effort; as one advances, self-esteem and coping capacity strengthen. Another poignant example contrasted mental and physical health by noting that an individual with a healthy body but poor mental wellbeing, such as someone struggling with substance use, may face greater challenges than a person with severe physical impairments but strong mental health. One participant explained mental wellbeing using the metaphor: "Even if you go in a Rolls-Royce from here to Vancouver or Toyota or Tesla or whatever you go in, the route is going to stay the same. The distance is going to be the same. But the perspective is... you are not going to enjoy the way there." This metaphor highlights how while external circumstances may remain unchanged, one's mindset can significantly influence their experience, suggesting that mental wellbeing is shaped not only by what happens to someone, but also by their outlook in navigating those experiences.

Even if you go in a Rolls-Royce from here to Vancouver or Toyota or Tesla or whatever you go in, the route is going to stay the same. The distance is going to be the same. But the perspective is...you are not going to enjoy the way there.

- Participant

Key Stressors Impacting Mental Wellbeing

Participants identified various stressors that negatively impact their mental health and wellbeing, including financial pressures, occupational issues, acculturation, family dynamics and social disconnection post COVID-19.

Financial strain was frequently raised as a pervasive source of stress, whereby increased costs of living have made financial stability difficult to attain for their families. One participant expressed that despite working continuously, “a man will still go into depression for sure”, depicting feelings of helplessness and loss of control in the face of escalating living costs and burden. Participants contrasted current experiences with the past, noting that mental stress was lower not only because of greater financial stability, but also due to fewer social expectations to achieve financial success. Social comparison and expectations were described as significant sources of stress in modern life, particularly in relation to participants’ roles as financial providers for their families. This stress is exacerbated when despite sustained effort and continuous work, they are unable to meet these socially valued standards of success.

Several occupational stressors within the trucking industry were identified, including workplace hierarchies, long and irregular working hours, lack of communication, and insufficient support. Participants highlighted a lack of fair work allocation where seniority influences hours assigned; those with less seniority often are assigned significantly fewer work hours despite their willingness to work. The reduction in available shifts limits their earning potential, leading to financial stress and burden. Participants also identified a lack of workplace support, noting that many truckers refrain from openly expressing their concerns due to a lack of responsiveness and support from management and colleagues. Despite attempts to raise issues, participants felt their concerns were often dismissed, resulting in unresolved problems and fostering a sense of helplessness and isolation within the workplace. Participants additionally expressed that the inherent nature of trucking which demands irregular work hours, posed significant challenges in maintaining wellbeing. With long shifts and frequent transitions between day and night schedules, many expressed limited time to spend with family and peers, which contributed to social isolation and weakened support networks.

Migration and acculturation was acknowledged as a significant stressor, whereby participants described the challenge of moving “from a separate land” into a “totally different culture”. They expressed a sense of dissonance, being

neither fully adapted to Canadian culture nor able to maintain their previous cultural practices. A participant expressed that although religious spaces like temples were present in Canada, they did not provide the same support or opportunities for communal dialogue as those in India.

Family and household dynamics were identified as another common stressor among participants. Marital tension and conflict is often exacerbated by occupational demands, while substance use, particularly alcohol, was described as a common coping response that simultaneously contributed to further conflict within the household. Participants additionally described extended family relationships as contributing to stress, conflict, and emotional insecurity, stemming from mistrust, social comparison, envy, and lack of support amidst relatives. Participants also expressed significant anxiety over their children in the context of rising rates of youth substance use, particularly cannabis, that has become normalized within school environments. They voiced distress over perceived gaps in supervision and accountability in institutions, and helplessness in navigating unfamiliar social norms related to substance use.

Building on concerns around youth substance use and institutional gaps, participants also expressed deep mistrust toward government policies and systems, particularly regarding drug legalization. Some viewed drug legalization policies as a governmental strategy to facilitate easier access to drugs and normalize their use. One participant even shared, “If you want pizza there is a 20 minute wait... if you want to order drugs the wait is 3 minutes.” Participants additionally highlighted that many systems and institutions are designed to serve the dominant White population, resulting in their unique experiences and challenges being neglected. Their distrust and frustration stem from systems that perpetuates social inequities and marginalizes minority communities, further exacerbating stress and impacting wellbeing.

If you want pizza there is a 20 minute wait... if you want to order drugs the wait is 3 minutes. - Participant

Lastly, participants brought up how the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on their social interactions and relationships had contributed to poorer wellbeing. One participant recounted an incident where a new trucking colleague refused to shake his hand on welcome due to fear of COVID transmission, which had led to feelings of offense on their part and eventual social distancing that

disrupted their traditional expressions of camaraderie in the workplace. Many participants acknowledged that even as the pandemic restrictions had subsided, they felt that social cohesion had not yet fully recovered. They reflected on the overall change in the nature of current social interactions, which are more virtual and digital, and less like the past, when they commonly had in-person meet-ups and gatherings where “anyone could meet anyone”. Participants noted that overall attendance at community gatherings and meetings have significantly declined post-pandemic, which has weakened social relationships and networks that they could otherwise depend on to improve their wellbeing.

Practices of Mental Wellbeing

Participants offered a range of behavioural, social, spiritual, and cognitive practices through which they manage their mental wellbeing, largely in response to ongoing life and occupational stressors.

Behavioural coping strategies encompassed what participants described as both constructive (positive) and maladaptive (negative) approaches. Swearing and alcohol use were described as common responses to occupational stress, and framed as normalized practices within the trucking environment, particularly following long or stressful workdays. Several participants noted that stopping at a liquor store after work was a routine way to “release” accumulated stress and decompress. Participants also described constructive coping strategies aimed at restoring their wellbeing, including physical activity (e.g., walking, exercise, badminton) and leisure activities (e.g., listening to music, reading, watching sports). Participants also noted that staying busy and completing routine chores (e.g., cooking, cleaning, home maintenance) were effective means of distraction that prevented rumination, thereby contributing to their wellbeing in the midst of stressors.

Many participants identified religion and spirituality as important supports for their mental wellbeing. Sikh religious practices including prayer, visiting the temple, reading Gurbani (Sikh scripture and religious teachings), remembering God (through reciting Waheguru), and participation in seva (selfless service), were described as effective methods for improving overall wellbeing. Participants described trust in divine will and acceptance of both happiness and suffering as sources of inner strength and emotional stability.

Social support emerged as a common source of strength, helping participants cope with stress and daily challenges. Participants described calling friends,

meeting regularly with small groups, and speaking openly with trusted peers as key ways to “let things out”. Family members, particularly parents, spouses and children, were identified as critical sources of support. Positive reassurance and affirmation from peers was highlighted as key in strengthening one’s mental wellbeing in times of stress, while collective support reinforced resilience during difficult periods.

Participants identified mindset as an important contributor to mental wellbeing. Practices that prioritize acceptance and contentment were described, such as avoiding social comparison, focusing on personal satisfaction, staying humble, and consciously choosing positivity. Participants also described strategies aimed at regulating emotional reactions, including remaining calm under pressure and not allowing negative emotions such as anger or jealousy to dominate one’s thoughts.

However, several participants acknowledged challenges and limitations in their approaches to managing their wellbeing. Some described feelings of frustration and exhaustion due to the difficulty of sustaining mental health practices consistently secondary to time constraints, such as breathing exercises and social gatherings. Family-related issues were also noted as ongoing stressors that hinder them from accessing social support within their family, which is otherwise a key source of wellbeing for them, thereby limiting an important way to improve their mental health.

Substance Use: Practices, Perceptions, and Challenges

Participants described a range of substances commonly used within their community, alongside nuanced understandings of substance use, social influences, and systemic issues affecting substance use and treatment.

Alcohol, marijuana, cigarettes, and smokeless or oral tobacco products (e.g., khaini and cool lip, traditional South Asian smokeless tobaccos placed between the lower or upper lip and gums) were frequently mentioned as part of everyday consumption. Participants tended to frame substance use along a continuum, as opposed to a strict dichotomy between “use” and “addiction”. Some participants compared substances such as alcohol or marijuana to everyday stimulants like coffee, suggesting that dependence or craving, rather than the substance itself, defined what constituted a “drug”.

Craving and withdrawal-like experiences were well understood, described as physical and psychological cues that signaled the need to use a substance, such as persistent thoughts about consumption, or physiological reactions when a substance is not taken. Addiction was discussed primarily in relation to the disruption of daily functioning, particularly work. Participants described how substance use influences their working hours, such as avoiding evening shifts in anticipation of drinking alcohol once a shift ends.

Peer influence was identified as playing a key role in shaping substance use behaviours. Participants shared that substance use often occurs in social contexts, and that it is less driven by individual desire but more so by encouragement or mere suggestion from peers. They shared that minimal prompting within trusted social circles is often a sufficient trigger to initiate substance use in a social setting. Many participants described that alcohol use primarily occurred in social settings or limited to weekends, highlighting that they did not feel the need or urge to drink outside of these situations.

Participants discussed experiences with treatment and support services, noting some negative encounters with treatment centers, while others expressed appreciation for integrated treatment approaches combining medical and counselling support. One participant recounted a negative past experience in which individuals were withdrawn from substances without appropriate medical supervision or follow-up care, resulting in severe distress and medical emergencies like seizures. Others described similar mistrust toward treatment centers, referring to them as overcrowded and poorly managed. Participants expressed preference for treatment combined with appropriate medical support and counselling.

Beyond individual treatment experiences, participants related substance use to systemic issues, expressing strong skepticism toward government policies regarding drug distribution and decriminalization. Participants felt that the decriminalization of drugs and expansion of treatment centers were part of a profit-driven system as opposed to a genuine effort to tackle root causes of substance use. They shared that underlying issues that contribute to substance use problems need to be addressed, such as lack of community support, social disconnection, and inadequate opportunities for wellbeing practices. Furthermore, participants showed pervasive concern regarding substance use among youth, describing vaping and other substances as highly prevalent and normalized within school environments. They expressed distress and anxiety about their children's early exposure to these substances, and emphasized the

significant influence of peer pressure on youth substance use. These concerns were further compounded by their perceptions of a lack of accountability and supervision by school boards and institutions, which they viewed as failing to effectively address or prevent substance use among students.

Implications and Recommendations

This report highlights the complex and intersecting challenges faced by South Asian truck drivers in the Lower Mainland, including occupational stressors, systemic inequities, cultural stigma, and limited access to culturally responsive mental health supports and resources. Trucking remains a high-risk profession with well-documented physical and psychological health impacts, which are further compounded for racialized immigrant workers navigating acculturative stress, precarious labour conditions, and societal stigma. The COVID-19 pandemic and its aftermath have additionally exacerbated these vulnerabilities, exposing structural gaps in the trucking industry such as worker protections, access to basic amenities, and public recognition of truckers' essential contributions.

The pilot mental health workshops validate the feasibility and acceptability of culturally responsive, community-based mental health interventions for South Asian truck drivers. Participants demonstrated strong engagement during the sessions, indicating willingness to engage in meaningful dialogue about mental health when provided with a culturally safe and affirming space. Their nuanced conceptualizations of mental wellbeing that encompass biological, emotional, social, spiritual, and cultural dimensions also reinforce the importance of moving beyond Western, individualistic models of mental health education. Instead, these findings highlight the value of culturally resonant approaches that integrate language, values, and practices to encourage meaningful engagement, reduce stigma and promote sustained participation. Specifically, culturally meaningful concepts such as collective wellbeing, spirituality, familial duties, and seva, should be incorporated into mental health services to cater to the lived experiences of South Asian men.

Furthermore, the findings highlight a critical role for mental health promotion in the trucking industry, emphasizing the need to recognize mental wellbeing as an integral component of occupational health and safety. Given the structural and occupational stressors that are inherent to trucking, industry stakeholders need to promote mental health education and support into workplace policies, training and resources. Community organizations such as

SAMHAA are well positioned to collaborate in delivering grassroots, culturally responsive interventions in the Lower Mainland, where the trucking workforce is predominantly South Asian, in ways that foster trust, promote meaningful engagement, and support sustained mental health and wellbeing.

As a pilot initiative, this intervention was limited by a small sample size and a restricted number of workshop sessions, which limits the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, group dynamics may have influenced the nature and depth of participant disclosure, especially given cultural norms surrounding privacy, masculinity, and stigma, that may have led participants to withhold more sensitive information, while dominant voices within the group may have influenced the direction of discussions. Nonetheless, this initiative has produced valuable insights that may serve to inform future program development and expansion.

Future efforts should aim to expand these workshops across multiple sites in the Lower Mainland, targeting truck drivers from diverse South Asian linguistic and cultural backgrounds. Increasing the frequency of workshops will also allow for trust and rapport to be fostered over time to ensure more meaningful engagement, as well as ensure consistent follow-up for sustained impact. Lastly, implementing robust evaluation methods to assess the effectiveness of the workshops would be valuable to inform program development and ensure measurable and meaningful outcomes.

South Asian truck drivers play a key role in sustaining Canada's economy and supply chains, yet are underserved and underrecognized. Addressing their mental health and wellbeing is essential not only for their personal health and for maintaining a safe and productive workforce, but also as a matter of social justice, ensuring equitable access to support and resources for a population that has historically been overlooked. This pilot project offers a promising model for engaging this community, demonstrating how culturally responsive, community-based interventions can effectively support the wellbeing of South Asian truck drivers.

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